

STUDIES IN LONG-CHAIN ACIDS. PART IV.

BY P. C. MITTER AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA.

Aleuritic acid, isolated from shellac, has been converted into epi-ambrettolic acid and epi-ambrettolide as well as ethyl 16-cyano- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate and homocivetinic acid.

Since the elucidation of the constitution of civetone (I) and muscone (II) as a result of the classical researches of Ruzicka, the study of the multinumbered ring systems has acquired a new importance

According to Luttringhaus and Ziegler (*Annalen*, 1937, 528, 181) the odour depends primarily on the size of the ring, the only condition being the presence of a place of disturbance (störungstelle) on the molecule. The nature of the 'place of disturbance' may differ widely in chemical character in being either a ketone, a lactone, an anhydride, ester, acetal or even an endocyclic imino grouping, without materially influencing the character of the odour. Polymethylene rings with fifteen to seventeen members and including one of these functional groups show throughout the odour of musk or of ambergris. With lower membered rings (C_{14}) the odour resembles cedar wood, while with still lower members the odour becomes camphoraceous.

Kerschbaum (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 902) has shown the presence of the lactone of ω -hydroxypentadecic acid (IIIa) and the lactone of ω -hydroxy- Δ^9 -hexadecic acid (III, $n=8$; $n^1=5$), ambrettolide in angelica root oil and in ambretto seed oil, the vegetable oils possessing odour of musk.

Whereas muscone is a saturated compound, civetone contains one double bond in the molecule, but the presence of the double bond has nothing to do

with the odour of the compound which has been found by Ruzicka to remain unchanged on saturation. A similar observation has been made by Kerschbaum (*loc. cit.*) with ambrettolide (III), where the saturation of the double bond does not alter the odour.

While *dl*-muscone has been synthesised by Ziegler and Weber (*Annalen*, 1934, 512, 164), and also by Ruzicka and Stoll (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 1308), the synthesis of civetone has not yet been accomplished. The chief reason for this is that the corresponding acid, namely Δ^9 -hexadecene-1 : 16-dicarboxylic acid (IV, $n=n'=7$) which should give this ketone on cyclisation can not be obtained with known synthetic methods. Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 1459) has, however, prepared a lower homologue of civetone by the distillation of the yttrium salt of Δ^9 -penta-decene-1 : 15-dicarboxylic acid (IV, $n=6$; $n'=7$) which he named civetic acid.

It has now been possible to develop a new method for the synthesis of the unsaturated acids of the type mentioned before, starting from aleuritic acid (V) which can be obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of shellac. A glance at the formula of aleuritic acid (V) and civetone (I) would show little relationship, but when it is considered that it is possible to convert aleuritic acid to a ω -halogenated Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid (VI, X=Halogen), it becomes at once clear that both civetic (IV, $n=6$; $n'=7$) and homocivetic acids (IV, $n'=n=7$) are synthesisable from it through the usual operations.

Considerable difficulties were encountered in the conversion of aleuritic acid into the desired halogenated acid (VI). When an ether suspension of aleuritic acid is treated with a solution of phosphorus di-iodide, ω -iodo- Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid (VI, X=I) is obtained. This method of double-bond formation has been extensively used by Kuhn and Winterstein (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 11, 87; cf. Kuhn, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 605) in the synthesis of polyenes.

The ω -iodo acid could not be purified. Its silver salt on being heated in xylene undergoes lactonisation, giving a seventeen-membered lactone (III, $n=6$; $n'=7$), which has been named epi-ambrettolide.

It is found to possess a musk-like odour but more fresh and floral as is commonly the case with lactones (*cf.* Kerschbaum, *loc. cit.*).

The corresponding hydroxy acid namely epi-ambrettolic acid (VI, $X=OH$) has been obtained in an impure state by acidification of the alkaline washings of the lactone. The acid could not be purified. Attempts to obtain the pure acid by hydrolysis of the acetyl derivative, prepared from the iodo-acid (VI, $Hal=I$) with potassium acetate, also failed, owing perhaps to the fact that the intermediate acetyl derivative could not be obtained pure. In the hope of purifying some of the intermediate products, the action of phosphorous di-iodide has been tried on ethyl aleuritrate. The process is found to be far more satisfactory as the iodo-ester can be purified by distillation. Acetylation with potassium acetate in acetic acid gives the corresponding acetyl derivative, which on hydrolysis with alcoholic potassium hydroxide gives the desired epi-ambrettolic acid, m.p. 55-55.6°, along with an impurity, m.p. 81-82°, having a much higher carbon content which is under investigation.

Attempts are made to condense the iodo-ester with sodiomalonic ester and potassium cyanide for synthesising homocivetic (IV $n=n'=7$) and civetic (IV, $n=6$; $n'=7$) acids. Unusual difficulties are, however, encountered in carrying out these apparently simple operations. The desired product could be obtained only under very specific conditions, the slightest variations leading to completely different products.

Condensation of the iodo-ester with ethyl sodiomalonate in alcohol results in the isolation of ethyl 16-ethoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate. When the reaction is carried out in benzene medium (*vide* experimental) the triester (VII) is formed which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation followed by esterification and distillation furnishes diethyl ester of homocivetic acid (IV, $n'=n=7$). The crude acid obtained by hydrolysis of the ester with methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide melts at 81-88°, the melting point being raised to 102.5-103.5° after three crystallisations from ethyl acetate. Ketone to civetone by distillation of the yttrium salt or through the dinitrile by the method of Ziegler will be taken up as soon as a sufficient quantity of the acid has been obtained.

The meagre solubility of crude iodo-ester in alcohol, coupled with its tendency to resinify, leads to poor yields in our attempt to replace the iodine by a cyano group. A number of conditions was tried *e.g.*, potassium cyanide in aqueous alcohol, in acetone or methyl ethyl ketone and silver

cyanide in benzene, but no satisfactory method could be found. The cyano-ester has not been obtained in sufficient quantity to study its hydrolysis to tivetïc acid.

The synthetical experiments, mentioned above, can not be regarded as complete, before the synthesis of aleuritic acid itself has been accomplished. Some progress towards the synthesis of this acid was made in this laboratory by Mitter and Dutt who synthesised ethyl 16-acetoxy-10-ketopalmitate (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 673).

Meanwhile we have achieved a partial synthesis by preparing 16-phenoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate (m.p. 59°) by the action of sodium phenate on the iodo-ester. We expected that this acid could be obtained synthetically by the reduction of $\text{PhO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{[CH}_2\text{]}_8\text{CO[CH}_2\text{]}_8\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ followed by dehydration and hydrolysis.

Unfortunately, the keto-ester could not be reduced either catalytically or with sodium and alcohol. Reduction with aluminium *isopropylate* gives a compound whose analytical data do not correspond with those required by the hydroxy ester.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Aleuritic Acid.—Lac (300 g.) was dissolved in 6*N*-potassium hydroxide (1350 g.) and left to stand for 4 days, when the potassium salt of the acid precipitated. It was filtered, washed with 6*N*-potassium hydroxide, and acidified with 10% ice cold sulphuric acid. The light yellow coloured acid was crystallised from water with a little charcoal, m.p. 100-101°. The yield was 10%.

ω-Iodo- Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid was prepared by adding a carbon-disulphide solution of phosphorus di-iodide to an ethereal suspension of aleuritic acid (10 g. in 60 c.c.). There was some effervescence and a sticky red solid was formed. After standing overnight ice was added and it was extracted with ether and washed with sodium thiosulphate. It was obtained as a thick oil, which could not be purified but was directly used for the next process.

Addition of solid phosphorus di-iodide (*cf.* Kuhn and Winterstein, *loc. cit.*) to an ethereal suspension of aleuritic acid gave inferior results.

Epi-ambrettolide was obtained by refluxing the silver salt of above iodo-acid, prepared as usual from the corresponding ammonium salt, in dry xylene for 36 hours in an oil-bath. The xylene solution was washed with *N/2*-potassium hydroxide and on removal of xylene a small quantity of an oil (b.p. 165°-175°/10 mm.) was obtained. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 10.5. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 76.2; H, 11.1 per cent).

The lactone possesses an intense odour of musk. It decolourises bromine in chloroform and permanganate solution. When freshly distilled it has got a light yellow colour but on standing assumes a brown colour.

Acidification of potassium hydroxide washing of the xylene solution gave *epi-ambrettolic acid* in very impure form.

Ethyl aleuritide was prepared from aleuritic acid using sulphuric acid as usual. The ester crystallised from ether, m.p. 50-55°. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 10.5. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 65.1; H, 10.84 per cent).

Ethyl 16-Iodo- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate.—To a suspension of ethyl aleuritide (20 g.) in dry ether (150 c.c.), a solution of phosphorus di-iodide in carbon bisulphide, prepared by gradually adding iodine (34 g.) to a solution of yellow phosphorus (4.2 g.) in the dry solvent (63 c.c.) was added slowly, a few c.c. at a time, with constant shaking. A sticky mass began to separate. It was then left overnight. The contents of the flask were poured on ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate and sodium thiosulphate. On treatment with sodium bicarbonate sometimes a heavy oily layer separated at the bottom. The iodo-ester has a great tendency to resinify. The ether-carbon bisulphide mixture was evaporated under pressure below 50°. It distilled at 180°/1.5 mm, yield 3 g. The yield remained the same when theoretical amounts of phosphorus and iodine were used. (Found: I, 30.3. $C_{18}H_{33}O_2I$ requires I, 31.1 per cent).

Ethyl 16-acetoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate was prepared by refluxing the iodo-ester (14 g.), potassium acetate (15 g.) and glacial acetic acid (45 c.c.) for 5 hours. The mixture was poured into water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate, dried and distilled at 190°/2 mm., yield 1 g. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 10.2. $C_{20}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 70.6; H, 10.6 per cent).

16-Hydroxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid (*epi-ambrettolic acid*) was obtained by the hydrolysis of the above acetoxy ester with methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%, 3 mols.), m.p. 55-55.5°. It has been observed that if the original iodo-ester is slightly impure, a substance is obtained at this stage, which on crystallisation from acetone and ethyl acetate melts

at 81-82°. This substance is under investigation. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 10.3. $C_{16}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 71.7; H, 11.2 per cent).

Ethyl Δ^9 -Hexadecene-1: 16 dicarboxylate (ethyl homocivetate).—A suspension of molecular sodium (0.56 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.) was cooled in ice and malonic ester (8 g.) was added to it drop by drop. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and ethyl 16-iodo- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate in benzene (15 c.c.) was added to the sodio-malonate. It was then allowed to stand one day, next heated at 50°-60° for 8 hours, then on the water-bath for 17 hours and finally in an autoclave for 5 hours at 150° in an atmosphere of alcohol. Benzene and alcohol were removed under low pressure.

To the liquid residue a solution of potassium hydroxide (15 g.) in alcohol (95%, 150 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 4 hours, when a red colour developed and the potassium salt of the tricarboxylic acid separated. The mixture was diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was next extracted with ether and then decarboxylated by heating for 1 hour up to 180°. The black tarry mass was esterified with alcohol (20 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (2 c.c., d. 1.84) by refluxing for 32 hours. The black mass was poured into ice and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate and distilled, b.p. 210°-215°/3 mm., yield 2.7 g. It is a thick oil, decolourising bromine immediately. (Found: C, 72.04; H, 10.85. $C_{22}H_{40}O_4$ requires C, 71.7; H, 10.9 per cent).

In an experiment where the condensation was carried out in an alcoholic solution in the following manner, ethyl 16-ethoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate was obtained.

The above iodo-ester (5 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of sodio-malonic ester (malonic ester, 1 c.c.; 0.24 g. of sodium and 4.7 c.c. of alcohol) and the mixture was heated in an autoclave for 2 hours at 145° and for 1½ hours at 150°. The alcohol was driven off and the residue extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate and distilled. A small quantity of a liquid, which decolourised bromine immediately, was obtained, b.p. 156°/1 mm., while the rest decomposed. (Found: C, 73.4; H, 11.1. $C_{20}H_{38}O_2$ requires C, 73.6; H, 11.6 per cent).

Δ^9 -Hexadecene-1: 16-dicarboxylic acid (homocivetate acid) was obtained by the hydrolysis of ethyl homocivetate (2.5 g.) with methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide (1.5 g. in 15 c.c.).

It crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 102.5°-103.5°. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 9.5. $C_{18}H_{32}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 10.2 per cent).

Ethyl 16-Cyano- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate.—The crude iodo-ester (10 g.) was refluxed with a solution of potassium cyanide (1.8 g.) in alcohol (95%,

90 c.c.) for 3 hours. The alcohol was evaporated off and the product was extracted with ether and distilled, b.p. $190^{\circ}/1$ mm., yield 0.15 g. It is waxy and decolourises bromine immediately, (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{24}H_{42}O_2N$ requires N, 4.56 per cent).

Ethyl 16-Phenoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoate.—A solution of the iodo-ester (10 g.) in hot alcohol was added to a solution of sodium phenate in alcohol (sodium, 0.56 g.; alcohol, 10 c.c.; phenol, 2.3 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux for 5 hours. On cooling the whole of the mass solidified. The alcohol was evaporated off and the residue was extracted with small quantities of ether. The ether was evaporated off and the residue distilled at $233-37^{\circ}/3$ mm., when a waxy solid, m.p. $41-43^{\circ}$, was obtained. It decolourises bromine immediately. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 9.68. $C_{24}H_{42}O$ requires C, 77.0; H, 10.16 per cent).

16-Phenoxy- Δ^9 -hexadecenoic acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of the above ester at the ordinary temperature with a 20% solution of potassium hydroxide (3 mols.) in methyl alcohol. After allowing to stand for 5 days the solution was acidified. The acid crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 59° .

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PALIT PROFESSOR'S LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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